

A METHODOLOGY FOR USING GENETIC ALGORITHMS AND FEA TO MINIMISE THE MASS OF LAMINATED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY: A method of using genetic algorithms together with finite element analysis to design for manufacture and minimise the mass of fibre reinforced symmetrically laminated structures with several design variables is described. The design constraint implemented is based on the Tsai-Wu failure criterion. Composite rectangular plates with eight layers are used to demonstrate the technique. Thus, the four fibre orientations and laminae thicknesses are to be determined optimally. In addition, the fibre orientations and layer thicknesses must be selected from a set of discrete (and commercially available) values.

KEYWORDS: FEA, Genetic algorithms, Fibre-reinforced laminates, Minimum mass

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that designs for structures fabricated from fibre-reinforced laminated composites can be tailored for additional advantage. Thus, for example, by using ply angles as design variables, and determining the optimal values to maximise or minimise criterion like strength or mass, the most benefit can be obtained from these materials. Due to manufacturing constraints, the sets of values from which the ply angles and layer thicknesses can be selected are generally discrete, and in such cases, the optimisation problem becomes one of finding the best permutation of these.

An important failure mode for laminated structures is bending under transverse loading. By selecting the stacking sequence and layer thicknesses optimally, the mass of a structure can be minimised for a given design strength constraint. Symmetrically laminated angle-ply configurations are often used as they avoid bending-stretching effects by virtue of mid-plane symmetry. One phenomenon associated with symmetric angle-ply configurations is the occurrence of bending-twisting coupling which may cause significantly different results as compared to cases in which this coupling is exactly zero [1]. The effect of bending-twisting coupling becomes even more pronounced for few layers. Due to this coupling, closed-form solutions cannot be obtained even for simple laminated plates, and thus many studies involving design optimisation of composite structures have neglected the effect. This study adopts a numerical approach to include the effect of bending-twisting coupling.

A number of studies concerning the minimum weight design of composite structures appear in the literature. For example, Walker *et al* [2] carried out an optimisation design study of laminated plates with the objective of minimising the deflection and weight, using finite element analysis and the *Golden Section* method, but this was limited to only two design variables, viz. fibre orientation and layer thickness. Angle-ply laminates subjected to uncertain loads were considered by Adali *et al* [3] who used a convex modelling approach in his analysis. Adali *et al* [4] investigated the minimum weight and deflection design of thick sandwich laminates via symbolic computation.

Genetic algorithms, which can be used to find the global solution of discrete optimisation problems, simulate the mechanics of natural genetics for artificial systems based on operations which are the counterparts of the natural type [5]. They use techniques derived from nature, and rely on Darwin's principle of survival of the fittest. When a population of biological species evolves over generations, characteristics that are useful for survival tend to be passed on to future generations, because individuals carrying them get more chances to breed. Individual characteristics in biological populations are stored in chromosomal strings. The mechanics of natural genetics are based on operations that results in structural yet randomised exchange of genetic information (ie. useful traits) between the chromosomal strings of reproducing parents, and consist of crossover and occasional mutation of the chromosomal strings. The reader is referred to Ref. 5 for further discussion of the standard genetic operators and theoretical properties of GAs.

Various authors have investigated the use of GAs for optimising composite structures. A minimum thickness design for plates with discrete ply angles subject to strength and buckling constraints was considered in the study by Kogiso *et al* [6], where a genetic algorithm search technique was used to achieve the optimal design. Tabakov [7] looked at multi-dimensional design optimisation of laminated structures, while Sivakumar [8] discussed the optimum design of laminated composite plates with cutouts. Other studies include that by Byon [9], who optimised hybrid thick-walled cylindrical shells under external pressure, and Nagendra [10], who used a GA to design stiffened composite panels.

Some researchers have reported the use of genetic algorithms to find the minimum mass of a structure. For example, Walker & Wilson [11] combined the finite element method with a GA to optimise laminated structures for maximum rigidity and minimum mass.

A technique for using GAs together with FEA to minimise the mass of fibre reinforced symmetrically laminated structures with several discrete design variables is described. The design constraint implemented is based on the Tsai-Wu failure criterion, although any suitable failure criterion can be implemented. Rectangular plates are used to demonstrate the method, have eight layers, and are symmetric about the midplane. Thus, the four fibre orientations and laminae thicknesses are to be determined optimally. To determine the best configuration, optimal ply angles for each layer are selected from amongst a predefined set of fibre orientations, commonly used in industry. This approach leads to cost-effective (and easier to construct) designs by virtue of allowing the use of standard composite plies. The most common orientations are 0°, 30°, 45°, 60° and 90°, which are the ones used in the present study. Also, the laminae thicknesses must be multiples of a standard ply, thickness; eg. 0.001m.

Results are presented for different load distributions, and various combinations of clamped, simply supported and free boundary conditions are considered. The effect of aspect ratio is also investigated. Initially, the mass of the structure was taken as the GA fitness parameter, but the number of initial genes required for convergence near the global minimum was large, and thus other measures were investigated. Some of these are presented, all demonstrating enhanced efficiency, but introduce problems to the study. Previous work on discrete optimisation of composite laminates include Ref. 6, and Refs 12 - 14.

BENDING OF RECTANGULAR LAMINATES

Consider a symmetrically laminated rectangular plate of length a , width b and thickness h under a transverse bending load $q(x, y)$, as shown in Fig. 1. The plate is located in the x, y, z plane and constructed of an arbitrary number K of orthotropic layers of thickness h_k and fibre orientation θ_k where $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$. The displacement of a point $(x^\circ, y^\circ, z^\circ)$ on the reference surface is denoted by $(u^\circ, v^\circ, w^\circ)$.

Fig. 1: Geometry and loading of the plate

The governing equation for the deflection w in the z direction under a transverse load q is given by [15]:

$$D_{11}w_{,xxxx} + 4D_{16}w_{,xxyy} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})w_{,xyyy} + 4D_{26}w_{,xyyy} + D_{22}w_{,yyyy} = q \quad (1)$$

where variables after the comma denote differentiation with respect to that variable, and

$$D_{ij} = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \bar{Q}_{ij}^{(k)} z^2 dz \quad (2)$$

are the bending stiffnesses and $\bar{Q}_{ij}^{(k)}$ are components of the transformed reduced stiffness matrix for the k^{th} layer. As no simplifications are assumed on the elements of the $[D]$ matrix, equation (1) includes bending-twisting coupling as exhibited by virtue of $D_{16} \neq 0, D_{26} \neq 0$.

OPTIMAL DESIGN PROBLEM

The objective of the design problem is to minimise the mass W of the laminated structure, subject to a failure criterion. The minimum mass is achieved by optimally determining the fibre orientations and the laminae thicknesses, given by $[\theta_1/ \theta_2/ \dots/ \theta_i \parallel t_1/t_2/ \dots/ t_i]_{\text{sym}}$. Thus, the design problem may be stated as:

$$W \min_{\theta, t} \equiv \min_{\theta, t} [W(\theta_i, t_i)], \theta_i \in (0^\circ, \pm 30^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, \pm 60^\circ, 90^\circ), i = 1, 2, \dots, K \quad (3)$$

where the thickness of each layer must be a multiple of a minimum feasible dimension. For example, if a standard ply thickness is $0.001m$, then each individual layer should have thickness $0.001k$, where $k \in N$.

Here, the mass is determined from the finite element solution of the problem given by $[K]\{\Delta\} - \{F\} = \{0\}$, and is used as the fitness parameter P by the GA. In this study, the Tsai-Wu failure criterion [17] is used which stipulates that the condition for non-failure for any particular ply is

$$F(\theta) = F_{11}\sigma_1^{(k)}\sigma_1^{(k)} + F_{22}\sigma_2^{(k)}\sigma_2^{(k)} + F_{66}\tau_{12}^{(k)}\tau_{12}^{(k)} + 2F_{12}\sigma_1^{(k)}\sigma_2^{(k)} + F_1\sigma_1^{(k)} + F_2\sigma_2^{(k)} \leq 1 \quad (4)$$

where the strength parameters $F_{11}, F_{22}, F_{66}, F_{12}, F_1$ and F_2 are given by

$$F_{11} = 1/(X_t X_c); F_{22} = 1/(X_t X_c); F_{66} = 1/G_2 \quad (5)$$

$$F_1 = 1/X_t - 1/X_c; F_2 = 1/Y_t - 1/Y_c; F_{12} = -\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{F_{11}F_{22}} \quad (6)$$

and X_b, X_c, Y_b, Y_c are the tensile and compressive strengths of the composite material in the fibre and transverse directions, and G is the in-plane shear strength.

Thus, the design problem can finally be explicitly stated as:

$$P_{\min} = \min_{\theta, t} |F - 1| \quad (7)$$

which follows from (3) and (4).

Finally, it is important to note that when alternative designs had equal mass, the best was that with the lowest failure index, and when alternative designs had equal failure indices, that with the lowest mass was selected.

RESULTS

Numerical results are given for a typical T300/5208 graphite/epoxy material [18] with $E_1 = 181$ GPa, $E_2 = 10.3$ GPa, $G_{12} = 7.17$ GPa and $\nu_{12} = 0.28$, $X_t = 1500$ MPa, $X_c = 1500$ MPa, $Y_t = 40$ MPa, $Y_c = 246$ MPa and $S = 68$ MPa. The symmetric plate is constructed of eight layers, viz. $[\theta_1/\theta_2/\theta_3/\theta_4 \parallel t_1/t_2/t_3/t_4]_{\text{sym}}$, and is subjected to a uniformly distributed load (UDL) over the entire surface. As already mentioned, the set of fibre orientations available to be used here is $(0^\circ, \pm 30^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, \pm 60^\circ, 90^\circ)$, while the set of layer thicknesses is $(0.00075m, 0.001m, 0.00125m, 0.0015m, 0.00175m, 0.002m, 0.00225m)$, leading to a total of $8^4 \cdot 7^4 = 9834496$ possible design candidates (chromosomes). For expedience, the thickness values will be discussed in terms of their millimetre equivalents; viz. 0.00225m will be reported as 2.25. Different combinations of free (F), simply supported (S) and clamped (C) boundary conditions are implemented at the four edges of the plate. In particular, five different combinations are studied, namely, (F,S,F,S), (F,S,C,S), (S,S,S,S), (C,S,C,S) and (C,C,C,C), where the first letter refers to the first plate edge, and the others follow in the anti-clockwise direction as shown in Fig. 1. Table 1 shows the influence of the boundary conditions on the optimal design of a plate with $a/b = 1$ (viz. each side is 1m long). Note that F is the value of the Tsai-Wu failure index for each design. Generally, one might expect that as the degrees of freedom are increased, so the mass should increase, but this is not true for the (C,S,C,S) and (F,S,C,S) plates, owing to the minimal number of variables (and thus appropriate combinations that lead to a low mass) available.

Table 1. Effect of boundary conditions on the optimal layup for plates with $a/b=1$ and UDL = 100kPa

Boundary Condition	Layup (thickness values in mm)	W (kg)	F
(F,S,F,S)	$(0^\circ/0^\circ/0^\circ/0^\circ \parallel 1/1/1/1)_s$	12.8	1
(F,S,C,S)	$(0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ \parallel 1.5/1.75/1.75/1.75)_s$	21.6	0.94
(S,S,S,S)	$(45^\circ/-45^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ \parallel 0.75/1.5/1.5/0.75)_s$	14.4	1
(C,S,C,S)	$(90^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/0^\circ \parallel 0.75/0.75/1/1)_s$	11.2	0.92
(C,C,C,C)	$(0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ \parallel 0.75/2/0.75/0.75)_s$	13.6	0.98

Improving the efficiency of the technique

In order to obtain the results given in Table 1, at least 60 parent chromosomes were necessary, and generally, at least 20 iterations were required in each case to produce the best design. To improve the efficiency of the technique, a few alternative fitness formulations were investigated. Two are briefly described next.

Alternative 1: $P = W \cdot F$

Since it is desirable to drive down both the mass and failure index as quickly as possible so that convergence to a global optimal design that meets the failure criterion is achieved efficiently (ie. with a minimum number of parents and generations), the first alternative fitness parameter that was considered was a product of the two, which generally worked very well (viz. the design problem becomes one of minimising P). In many cases, as few as 40 parents (that must be carefully chosen) could be used, and in addition, because of the formulation, it was not necessary to dispose of any genes (design candidates) that did not meet the failure criterion, as long as the final result did. Unfortunately, other problems were introduced by the new fitness formulation. If

P was used to select the best design candidate from the list of alternatives after convergence was obtained, sometimes a gene having a greater mass but a fitness value of less than another gene with less mass resulted. Thus, after convergence, it is important to select the best gene from the list based on mass only (after making sure that it complies with the failure criterion).

Table 2 shows the influence of the aspect ratio on the optimal layup and thickness for (F,S,C,S) plates with the same loading as before. The results in this table were generated using the fitness parameter $P = W.F$. As expected, as the aspect ratio increases, so the mass increases. For the plates with aspect ratios of 1.5 and 2, very few candidates had a failure index of 1 or below. Therefore the choice of optimal candidates was minimal.

Table 2. Effect of aspect ratio on the optimal layup for (F,S,C,S) plates with UDL = 100kPa

a/b	Layup (thickness values in mm)	W (kg)	F
0.5	(0°/45°/-45°/90° 0.75/0.75/0.75/1.25) _s	5.6	0.88
0.75	(0°/90°/0°/90° 0.75/1/1.25/1.75) _s	11.4	1
1	(0°/90°/0°/90° 1.5/1.75/1.75/1.75) _s	21.6	0.94
1.5	(60°/-60°/60°/-60° 2/2/2.25/2.25) _s	40.8	1
2	(90°/60°/-45°/60° 2/2.25/2.25/2.25) _s	56	0.99

Alternative 2: $P = W - F$

Because of the problem introduced by the first alternative design formulation, a second was considered. By reformulating the fitness as $P = W - F$ (viz. the design problem is still one of minimising P , but now P can be negative), the frequency with which the problem occurred reduced, but still remained. Nonetheless, as before, as few as 40 parents could be used, and convergence often took place within 4 or 5 generations. Table 3 shows the effect of a patch load (which covers only a quarter of the surface) for (F,S,C,S) plates with $a/b = 1$ and $a/b = 2$. The results in this table were generated using the fitness parameter $P = W - F$. As can be seen, the mass of the plates with patch loads (viz. with 1/4 of the total load of the UDL plates) is about half that of the UDL plates.

Table 3. Effect of load type on the optimal layup for square (F,S,C,S) plates, and load magnitude of 100kPa

a/b	Load Type	Layup (thickness values in mm)	W (kg)	F
1	Patch	(0°/45°/-45°/90° 0.75/0.75/1/0.75) _s	10.4	0.85
1	UDL	(0°/90°/0°/90° 1.5/1.75/1.75/1.75) _s	21.6	0.94
2	Patch	(0°/0°/90°/90° 0.75/0.75/0.75/1.5) _s	24	0.83
2	UDL	(90°/60°/-45°/60° 2/2.25/2.25/2.25) _s	56	0.99

CONCLUSIONS

A technique for using genetic algorithms together with finite element analysis to design for manufacture and minimise the mass of fibre reinforced symmetrically laminated structures with several design variables is described. The design constraint implemented is based on the Tsai-Wu failure criterion, although any suitable one can be substituted. The present study adopts a numerical approach to include the effects of bending-twisting coupling etc, and the finite element

formulation used is based on Mindlin theory, although, once again, any suitable formulation can be substituted. Composite rectangular plates with eight layers are used to demonstrate the technique. Thus, the four fibre orientations and laminae thicknesses are determined optimally. In addition, the fibre orientations and layer thicknesses are selected from a set of discrete (and commercially available) values. Results were presented for different load distributions, and various combinations of clamped, simply supported and free boundary conditions were considered. The effect of the aspect ratio was also investigated.

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